

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva

Student of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Turdiyeva Umidaxon O'rol qizi

Student of the Faculty of Economics and Tourism of Termiz State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7438584>

Abstract. *This article discusses the use of pedagogical technologies in English language teaching, their advantages and positive effects on the development of students' communicative competence. Such technologies give an opportunity to develop students' creative independence, teach them to work with various sources of knowledge. In addition, it provides some non-traditional forms of conducting English lessons.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, pedagogical technologies, non-traditional methods, teaching process, communicative approach, information technologies, methodology, interactivity, communal duty.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается использование педагогических технологий в обучении английскому языку, их преимущества и положительное влияние на развитие коммуникативной компетенции студентов. Такие технологии дают возможность развивать творческую самостоятельность учащихся, обучают их работе с различными источниками знаний. Кроме того, предусмотрены некоторые нетрадиционные формы проведения уроков английского языка.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативная компетентность, педагогические технологии, нетрадиционные методы, учебный процесс, коммуникативный подход, информационные технологии, методика, интерактивность, коллективный долг.*

Introduction: The task of the teacher is to create practical skills with the English language for each student, to choose pedagogical teaching methods that allow each student to show their activity and creativity. It is important that the teacher, in cooperation with the student, using the methodology of the lesson project and new information technologies, should organize a meaningful lesson that helps to increase the level of education, individualization, and knowledge of students, taking into account the abilities of pedagogical technologies, Internet resources.

The relational approach is a strategy that stimulates communication, the goal of which is to consciously understand the material and spiritual ways of communicating with students. This technology is not so difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet.

In order for a communal task to be completed, a problem or question for discussion must arise, and in this discussion students can not only exchange information, but also evaluate the problem. The main criterion that distinguishes this approach from other types of activities is that students choose a language unit to express their thoughts.

In the international approach, it is better to use the Internet, because its purpose is to study English and learn the language by expanding the knowledge and experience of the

students. One of the main requirements for learning English using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is called the usual method of interactivity.

Interactivity is the organization, coordination and completion of mutual goals and the result of speech means. The student can use interactivity to learn activities in his native language, and to develop Internet skills. Also, there is a real interest in learning vocabulary and grammar, so such technologies are effective. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond adequately in English.

One of the technologies that offer private lessons is the project method, a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity, and independence. The typology of this technology project is different. In doing so, the student should engage in mixed projects with various scientific-research, creative, practical-oriented and informational features in real practice. The work of the project is a multi-level approach to learning the language of reading, auditing, speaking and grammar. The method of the project greatly contributes to the development of active independent thoughts in students. Preparing projects, teaching children to cooperate and preparing cooperation will increase mutual assistance and creative abilities. At the same time, the essence of innovative education in learning the English language is that the educational process involves almost all students in the learning process, and the use of new pedagogical technologies increases the quality of the lesson.

For example, we can mention the following pedagogical technologies:

"Carousel" technology. Like many innovative technologies, carousel pedagogical technology is one of the effective methods. Learners work in this technology as follows, usually a large number of participants are required to participate. They should form two loops: inner and outer. On the outside of the inner ring, stationary students play, and on the outside, the outer students who rotate every 30 seconds play. Thus, they have time to speak for a few minutes and choose the interlocutor from their right side and try to convince them. Dialogues of a Laoretic nature are perfectly valid, the topic can be dating, nationality, conversation in a public place, etc. Students talk excitedly, this technology is dynamic and effective.

"Theatre" technology. It is a performance-like technology in which the audience, experts, critics and analysts participate. A few students play in the situation in the circle, the rest observe and analyze. Spectators' task is that they should raise the mood and emotions of the critics, and they should play roles in accordance with the character of the audience, based on what they have followed, they should tell their conclusions.

"Sociological survey" technology. It involves students moving through the account to collect information on the proposed topic as they move. Each participant receives a list with tasks. The teacher helps to formulate questions and answers, ensures that the interaction begins with English.

"Proposal in progress" technology. Students should read their unfinished sentences and can continue with any word. The first idea that comes to mind is suggested. The prompts start very vaguely, so listeners have almost unlimited options to complete it. They relate to different areas of life and can cover any topics.

"Group story" technology. This technology is implemented in two different ways. In the first method, each student adds one sentence to the already started story. At a certain signal (after one minute), a sheet with an unfinished story is sent in the merge. The second method is very suitable for the development of the topic. The teacher asks questions in a certain order, each

participant of the process writes an answer, no one can see it or help their neighbor. The movement takes place in a circle. So, you get a few surprises at the end.

"Can you believe it..." technology. This type of language practice can be used on any subject. And in this it is suggested that the student should first "trust" his teacher, and then get acquainted with their statements within a certain topic.

"Brain loop" technology. It is a technology that is perfect for all classes. Materials studied in this technology should be universal collections. The content of the types can be completely different and these sections include vocabulary, grammar, reading, listening and writing. This technology requires seriousness. This technology includes: formalizing the task, creating a presentation, focusing and thinking about questions, answers, diplomas, etc. At the beginning of the game, it is necessary to choose the jury, there will be an option for students to participate. Each round lasts 3 minutes, after which the answers will be submitted to the jury. The correctness of the answers is checked and discussed after each round. Then a number of questions can bring additional points to the teams.

It is known from the above technologies that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. With this assurance, teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the trainings held during the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and freely, and their determination will be trained.

Conclusion: Summarizing the above, it is clear that the key to successful speech activity of students is skillful use of non-traditional forms of lessons by teachers conducting pedagogical technologies. In this, students join the culture of the studied English-speaking countries, expand the knowledge of the cultural heritage of the people of their native country, which allows them to actively participate in the dialogue of cultures.

REFERENCES:

1. Bakhrom, K., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). THEORETICAL BASICS FOR ENGLISH TEACHING. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 157-158.
2. Danny Gagnon, Developing Effective Communication Skills, Montreal University, 2011.
3. G. Djumambetova, B. Khabibullaeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 106-107. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7005635
4. Galsky N. D. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages, M.: ARKTI, 2003.
5. Jumaeva Mukarrama, Azimov Jasurbek, & Saidov Kamoliddin. (2022). TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS IN ENGLISH. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(06), 252–255. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/HB7Y9>
6. Jumayeva, M. (2022). ISLOM MA'RIFATINING TA'LIM-TARBIYA SIVILIZATSIYASIGA TA'SIRI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(8), 41–44. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/3419>
7. Jumayeva, Mukarrama Bekzodovna (2022). OLIY TA'LIMDA INNOVATION USUL VA VOSITALAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (Special Issue 20), 214-226. doi: 10.24412/2181-1784-2022-20-214-226
8. Lustig Myron W., Koester Jolene. *Intercultural Competence: Interpersonal Communication Across Cultures*, Pearson, Boston, 6th Edition, 2010.
9. M. Jumayeva (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 711-714. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7264531
10. M. Jumayeva (2022). EFFECTIVE CREATIVE WAY OF ERKIN VAHIDOV. TRANSLATOR, POET, HERO OF UZBEKISTAN.. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 404-409. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7059373
11. M. Jumayeva (2022). UYG'ONISH DAVRI ALLOMALARINING PEDAGOGIKA VA TA'LIMTARBIYAGA O'ZGACHA YONDASHUV ASOSIDAGI QARASHLARI TAHLILI. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 26-29. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6990805
12. M. Jumayeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF FEATURE FILMS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 581-583. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7257719
13. M. Jumayeva, & M. Mahmudova (2022). INGLIZ TILIDA TALAFFUZNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 263-265. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7027100
14. Maxmudjonov Ibroximjon, & Jumayeva Mukarrama. (2022). HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(5), 178–182. Retrieved from <https://involta.uz/index.php/iv/article/view/119>
15. Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva (2021). INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS. *Scientific progress*, 2 (4), 881-885.
16. Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva, & Mahmudova Madina Shukhratovna (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH GRAMMAR. Science and innovation, 1 (Special Issue 2), 608-611. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7368578

17. Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva, & Shaymardanova Mukhlisa Usmanovna (2022). PRACTICAL METHODS OF CULTURE-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Science and innovation*, 1 (Special Issue 2), 612-615. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7368582.
18. Turdieva Umidaxon, & Jumaeva Mukarrama. (2022). SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE AS A FACTOR IN DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM SPHERE. *Academic Research Journal*, 1(3), 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880388>
19. Umidjon, G., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). USED IN LESSON PROCESSES EFFICIENCY OF INTERACTIVE METHODS. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 161-162.
20. Zaripova Donoxon Kamiljanovna, Abdisheribov Sulaymon Javlonbek O'G'Li, & Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva (2022). THE ANALYSIS OF HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS. *Science and innovation*, 1 (Special Issue 2), 672-676. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7369006